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Fault Tolerance and Fallback Strategies in Connected and Automated Vehicles: A Review

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ABSTRACT Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) are considered the future of transportation, offering increased safety, efficiency, and convenience. However, their reliance on sophisticated sensors and complex algorithms poses challenges, especially in scenarios with uncertainties, constraints, or failures. Dynamic Driving Task (DDT) fallback and fault tolerance strategies serve as critical mechanisms to ensure safe operation when primary systems fail or face functional insufficiencies. This paper provides an analysis of the fault-related taxonomy established by international standards and a comprehensive review of the DDT fallback and fault tolerance strategies used in CAVs, focusing on their strategy, classification, and implementation methods. Moreover, the challenges and future research directions for the development and improvement of fault tolerance strategies are discussed. The analysis shows that the main trends are to avoid the termination of the CAV operation in case of a failure or functional insufficiency, or at least to be able to guide the vehicle to a safe state. However, there is a tendency towards the possibility of continuing the operation. This review contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of DDT fallback and fault tolerance strategies for CAVs and future trends.

INDEX TERMS Connected and Automated Vehicles, Fallback, Fault tolerance, Functional Insufficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

ROAD traffic accidents cause approximately 1.19 million deaths per year, nearly 3260 every day. They are the leading killer of children and youth aged 5 to 29 years, as well as the 12th leading cause of death when all ages are considered [1]. Moreover, these accidents are largely preventable. A significant proportion of crashes in the USA can be attributed to human error (e.g., recognition, decision, and performance errors), which accounts for over 90% of crashes. The remaining leading factors are related to the environment (e.g., slick roads, glare) and the vehicle

(e.g., tires, wheels, brakes) [2]. In the past few decades, Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) have demonstrated their capacity to enhance safety, efficiency, and comfort, and are projected to become a pivotal component of the solution to this societal problem. The European Commission has asserted that ITS could significantly enhance road safety, facilitate mobility for individuals who are unable to operate vehicles independently (e.g., the elderly or people with disabilities), and promote the establishment of car-sharing structures and Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) [3]. Consequently,

ITS solutions have recently received increasing attention from academic and industrial circles.

The developments of ITS components have enabled the commercialization of SAE Level 2 vehicles [4], paving the way for higher driving automation levels, including conditional and full driving automation (i.e., SAE Level 3+). Achieving Level 4 is a complex task that, in addition to the technical challenge, is subject to ethical and regulatory concerns [5]. As part of the ITS, Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) are complex safety-critical systems, susceptible to dangerous situations caused by system failures or design limitations. The resilience and defensive methods of CAVs are considered a requirement for achieving safety and security [6]. Furthermore, the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) has identified the necessity to develop test methods, procedures, and criteria to assess long-term safety benefits [7].

Given the safety-critical nature of CAVs, fault tolerance emerges as a critical capability. This emphasizes the necessity to prevent hazardous situations while operating under acceptable risk levels. Researchers have explored various approaches to enhance the safety and resilience of CAVs when operating outside their designed conditions or facing unexpected situations, recognizing the potential risks involved. However, as highlighted by Stolte *et al.*, the terminology used across technical contributions and international standards to describe the capabilities of the CAVs while operating in the different forms of fault tolerance is inconsistent [8].

A few earlier literature reviews focusing on specific components or subsystems are available. The review published by Chougule *et al.* is centered in examining the limitations inherent in CAVs, as well as their impact in accidents [9]. Ceccarelli *et al.* reviewed RGB camera failures and their effects on the CAVs [10]. Zidan *et al.* conducted a review of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) vulnerabilities and existing solutions [11]. The work presented by Zhu *et al.* focuses on GNSS position integrity in urban environments [12]. Gilroy *et al.* is centered on the problem of occlusions in the perception of the environment [13]. Huang *et al.* reviewed fault tolerance in steer-by-wire systems [14]. The review published by Wang *et al.* analyses the most used safety metrics in the context of CAVs [15]. In Ju *et al.*, attack detection and resilience approaches for CAVs from vehicle dynamics and control perspectives are reviewed [16]. Morales-Alvarez *et al.* presented a review centered on Take Over Request (TOR) as the fault tolerance approach [17].

After a thorough literature review, no literature review covers Dynamic Driving Task (DDT) fallback and handling approaches in CAVs from a fault tolerance regime classification perspective. This literature review is meant to cover this gap. Hence, the main contributions of this manuscript can be described as follows:

- It summarizes the fault-related terminology for CAVs established by the International Standards under a

cause/strategy criteria and categorizes between strategies that propose a continuation of operation and the ones that propose safe stops in the event of system failure or insufficiency.

- An in-depth examination of the state of the art by following the above criteria is carried out, extracting trends and common terminology to categorize the literature.
- The most relevant contributions are analyzed and categorized, accompanied by a detailed account of the handling strategy, the validation environment, and the Operational Design Domain (ODD).
- The current state of the fault tolerance techniques in the ITS field is collected, and the potential areas for future exploration are identified.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the taxonomy of fault tolerance in CAVs and the methodology employed in this literature review are detailed. Next, the most prevalent concepts of fault tolerance strategies in CAVs, as identified in this study, are presented in detail in Section III. Section IV presents a general description and classification of degradation and operational strategies after failures and functional insufficiencies. Next, an analysis of the DDT fallback strategies for localization failures is presented in Section V. Section VI provides an insight into the publicly available fault tolerance approaches done by the industry. In Section VII, some reflections and discussions are presented. Finally, Section VIII covers the conclusion.

II. TAXONOMY AND METHODOLOGY

A. TAXONOMY

International standards play a crucial role in establishing a common language and framework for ensuring the safety and reliability of connected and automated vehicles. Among these standards, key documents such as SAE J3016 [4], ISO 26262 [18], ISO 21448 [19], and ISO/TR 4804 [20] introduce several safety-related terms and definitions, which are followed throughout this manuscript.

According to SAE J3016 (Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles) [4], a *Dynamic Driving Task (DDT) performance-relevant system failure* is a malfunction that prevents the driving automation of performing a portion of the DDT. Furthermore, it introduces the concepts of *failure mitigation strategy* and *DDT fallback*. A *failure mitigation strategy* refers to a vehicle function that brings an automated vehicle to a controlled stop in the path after the occurrence of a *system failure* that incapacitates the Automated Driving Systems (ADS) (e.g., stop in place). By contrast, the term *DDT fallback* is used when the ADS is capable of achieving a *minimal risk condition* after the occurrence of a *system failure* or upon an ODD exit (e.g., exiting the active lane). The *minimal risk condition* is defined as a stable and stopped condition that reduces the risk of a crash when a given trip cannot be continued.

Even though both terms look similar, they should not be confused. The main difference between *failure mitigation strategy* and *DDT fallback* is the system that performs the controlled stop. In the first, it is the vehicle, not the ADS, that performs the controlled stop. Thus, the maneuver may produce a dangerous situation, and safety is not guaranteed. Conversely, in the second, the ADS continues operating after the *system failure*, and it is capable of executing a maneuver that brings the vehicle to a stopped condition. This maneuver may involve continuing driving for a limited amount of time. The presence of a complete *DDT fallback* strategy is the differential component between a Level 3 and a Level 4 ADS.

The ISO 26262 standard (Road vehicles – Functional safety) is focused on the functional safety of electrical and electronic systems within road vehicles [18]. More precisely, it is a standard with a wider scope than automated vehicles. The standard includes the definition of *emergency operation*, which is stated as the operating mode that provides safety after the occurrence of a *fault* until the transition to a *safe state* has been completed. Another contribution is the *emergency operation tolerance time interval*, defined as the period during which the emergency operation can be maintained. This standard also introduces the concepts of *degradation*, defined as the transition of an element to a state with reduced functionality or performance, and *fault tolerance*, defined as the ability to maintain a specific functionality in the presence of one or more *faults*. Furthermore, the standard explicitly distinguishes between *fault* and *failure*. *Fault* is defined as the abnormal condition that leads an item (i.e., ADS) to fail, whereas *failure* is the termination of the intended behavior of an item due to a *fault*.

The scope of the ISO 21448 standard (Road vehicles – Safety of the intended functionality -SOTIF-) is to guide the design, verification, and validation measures to achieve an absence of unreasonable risk due to hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies [19]. Consequently, this standard does not handle system failures but focuses instead on minimizing the risk produced by a *functional insufficiency*, such as incomplete perception of the scene (e.g., occlusions), insufficiency of the decision algorithm, or insufficient performance of actuation. ISO 21448 also enlarges the application of the term *DDT Fallback*, which can be used not only after a *system failure* but also after a *functional insufficiency*.

Although the definitions provide an essential framework for handling system failures in CAVs, the aforementioned standards exclude terminology related to fault tolerance techniques. This gap is covered by ISO/TR 4804 (Road vehicles – Safety and cybersecurity for automated driving systems) [20], which defines the terms *fail-safe*, *fail-degraded* and *fail-operational*, used to describe the different capabilities of CAVs after the occurrence of a fault. *Fail-safe* is defined as the property of an ADS to execute a *minimal risk manoeuvre* to achieve a *minimal risk condition* and a *safe state* in the event of a *failure*. By contrast, *fail-degraded* is defined

FIGURE 1. Taxonomy of safety-related terms found across the standards SAE J3016, ISO 26262, ISO 21448 and ISO/TR 4804. The terms are categorized in Cause of the emergency and Strategy against it.

as an *item* that can operate with reduced functionality in the presence of a fault. *Item* is referred as a system or combination of systems that implement a function or part of a function at a vehicle level. Finally, a *fail-operational item* can maintain its full intended functionality in the presence of a fault. It should be noted that while *fail-degraded* and *fail-operational* are applied at the *item* level, *fail-safe* is defined at the ADS level.

Stolte *et al.* identified that these concepts are often used and interpreted differently in the literature [8]. Due to the unclear usage of these terms, the authors proposed a unified taxonomy to provide a clearer demarcation of the fault tolerance terminology. However, this proposal is not recognized at the international level, so in this manuscript, the taxonomy defined by the standards is considered for the analysis.

An overall view of the taxonomy proposed by the aforementioned standards is depicted in Fig. 1, highlighting the origin of the terminology and classifying the terms depending on whether they are causes of the emergency or handling strategies to safely overcome the causes. The works targeting DDT Fallback strategies and fault-tolerant techniques against system failures and functional insufficiencies are the scope of this review.

The definitions of Fig. 1 are provided for clarity and reference throughout this document:

- (*DDT performance-relevant*) *System failure*: A malfunction in a driving automation system and/or other vehicle system that prevents the driving automation system from reliably performing its portion of the DDT on a sustained basis, including the complete DDT, that it would otherwise perform.
- *Functional Insufficiency*: Insufficiency of specification or performance insufficiency; Limitation of the technical capability contributing to a hazardous behaviour or inability to prevent or detect and mitigate reasonably foreseeable indirect misuse when activated by one or more triggering conditions.
- *Failure Mitigation Strategy*: A vehicle function (not an ADS function) designed to automatically bring an

ADS-equipped vehicle to a controlled stop in path following either: (1) prolonged failure of the fallback-ready user of a Level 3 ADS feature to perform the fallback after the ADS has issued a request to intervene, or (2) occurrence of a system failure or external event so catastrophic that it incapacitates the ADS, which can no longer perform vehicle motion control in order to perform the fallback and achieve a minimal risk condition.

- **DDT Fallback:** Response by the driver or automation system to either perform the dynamic driving task (DDT) or transition to a minimal risk condition (MRC) after the occurrence of a failure(s) or detection of a functional insufficiency or upon detection of a potentially hazardous behaviour.
- **Minimal Risk Condition:** Vehicle state in order to reduce the risk, when a given trip cannot be completed.
- **Fault tolerance:** Ability to deliver a specified functionality in the presence of one or more specified faults.
- **Fail-safe:** Property of an automated driving system to achieve a minimal risk condition and to achieve a safe state in the event of a failure.
- **Fail-Degraded:** Property of the item to operate with reduced functionality in the presence of a fault.
- **Fail-Operational:** Property of the item to maintain its full intended functionality in the presence of a fault.

B. METHODOLOGY

This work follows the methodology depicted in Fig. 2. First, an initial search of the literature was made in scientific databases, including Google Scholar, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore, using various search keywords such as “fallback strategies for automated vehicles”, “fault tolerance”, “fail-operational” and “fail-safe”. The search was enhanced using Elicit [21], an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based tool for finding related articles. The tool was also used to extract a large list of concepts from the obtained literature. Afterward, the efforts were directed toward manually filtering and labeling the concepts in groups and techniques. Next, the literature was classified according to the aforementioned concepts, producing the first iteration of Table 1.

The main conclusion extracted after analyzing the contributions classified in Table 1 relates to the different approaches found in the literature. On the one hand, some works propose strategies to continue the operation, in a degraded or operational mode, after a system failure or a functional insufficiency, where the system does not fail but is not capable of performing safely to scenario-specific triggering events, and harm could be produced. On the other hand, other works focus on developing fallback strategies for system failures, i.e., controlled transitions to a minimal risk condition, where the operation is concluded.

Table 2 gathers the works that propose approaches that intend to maintain a degraded or full operation after a system failure or functional insufficiency, whereas the fallback

FIGURE 2. Methodology followed in the review.

strategies that bring the vehicle to a minimal risk condition are collected in Table 3.

At this point, the keywords used in the search were enlarged with module-specific ones such as “fallback localization”, “dead-reckoning”, “degraded localization”, “fault-tolerant control”, “remote driving”, “planning fault” and “sensor fusion”. Some other AI-based tools, such as Inciteful [22], Litmaps [23], and Research Rabbit [24], were used to build relationship maps, as well as to find similar works. Furthermore, the concepts gathered in Table 1 were iterated and completed during the completion of this work, covering an initial search period between March 2023 and June 2024. Additional literature was collected from July 2024 through April 2025 to collect the most recent works.

III. FAULT-RELATED TERMINOLOGY IN CAVS

The literature presents a variety of terminology related to system failures and functional insufficiencies. Despite the lack of a uniform understanding of the fault tolerance regimes, as explained by Stolte *et al.* [8], the reviewed literature shows common patterns regarding the studied failure or insufficiency, the handling approach, or the used methods.

The terminology that has been gathered is presented in Table 1, and is structured according to the following format. The common patterns and terminology are binary classified as *Causes* or *Strategies*, and are divided into eight different groups (i.e., *Sensors*, *Ego vehicle localization*, *Perception*, *Decision/Planning*, *Control*, *Communication*, *Driver-Vehicle Interaction* and *Vehicle*) depending on the nature of the term. Besides, the terms are binary classified as causes of the

emergency or strategies to overcome them. Furthermore, the references whose proposal can be labeled as one of the fault tolerance terms depicted in Fig. 1 (i.e., *Fail-Operational-(FO)*), *Fail-Degraded-(FD)*, or *Fail-Safe-(FS)* are classified accordingly. The classification is made so that a given article may belong to a *Cause* term, if it focuses on detection or identification, to a *Strategy* term, if it addresses a given failure or insufficiency, or to both, if it proposes a complete detection and handling pipeline for a given problem.

A. SENSORS

The group sensors encompass those concepts that fall under the acquisition group, leaving the algorithms used to extract information from the sensors out of scope [152]. Proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors are responsible for measuring the state of the ego-vehicle and its surroundings, respectively. Nevertheless, the sensors can exhibit unexpected behavior due to environmental conditions or system failures, which can affect the operation of the CAV. The literature contains a collection of works [25]–[36] that focus on the **Sensor error detection** of proprioceptive (e.g., IMUs, wheel speed sensors, speedometer) and exteroceptive sensors (e.g., cameras, LiDAR, radar), using comparison with the outputs of similar sensors or methods to estimate the same variable.

Some contributions propose to perform a **Sensor isolation** to eliminate the identified defective sensor and avoid further propagation of the measurement [25], [27], [34]. Finally, some **Sensor correction** techniques, such as deep learning and human-based learning, are addressed in some CAVs-specific literature [37]–[40], although many contributions belong to the more general robotics literature [153], [154].

B. EGO VEHICLE LOCALIZATION

The capability of localizing the ego vehicle is of paramount importance for the successful operation of a CAV. Consequently, the group ego vehicle localization encompasses those works that either propose a solution in the event of a localization failure or have the fault-tolerant approach comprised in the localization group.

GNSS are one of the most recurrent sources of vehicle localization. They provide accuracy in the range of a few centimeters when operating with good satellite visibility and receive Real Time Kinematic (RTK) corrections. Nevertheless, **GNSS faults** are a well-known problem, and their localization capabilities may not be enough in certain scenarios such as urban roads or forested environments due to limited satellite visibility, multipath effect, interferences, and foliage attenuation, causing signal degradation. Furthermore, they are subject to external threats like jamming and spoofing attacks. The literature comprehends a variety of approaches that are designed to work after a GNSS fault [25], [27], [29], [37], [40]–[50], [52]–[55], [57]–[60].

Point cloud map-based LiDAR localization algorithms are currently one of the most widely used configurations, particularly in urban environments, tunnels or forested roads,

where the GNSS tends to degrade their performance. The implementation of cloud-point matching or registration algorithms necessitates the use of a globally referenced high-definition map, which has limitations as it is susceptible to faults and inaccuracies. The primary cause for **LiDAR localization faults** in the literature are inaccurate or modified point-cloud maps, as well as map-less zones [27], [29], [48], [55], [61].

The incorrect implementation of fusion algorithms or natural but rare phenomena (e.g., solar flares or electric storms) may cause a **Data fusion fault** [25]. Most of **Localization sources fusion** approaches utilize variants of Kalman filtering to overcome temporal degradations of each source to provide stable, resilient, and precise localization service [41], [43]–[48], [55], [59]–[61]. Furthermore, another trend is identified in the literature, comprising works that perform a **Localization source switch** to a healthy and independent localization pipeline (e.g., using LiDAR localization when the GNSS is unavailable) [29], [49], [50], [53]. Finally, other works propose using **AI-based odometry** as a solution to the localization problem in the presence of exteroceptive sensor faults. These approaches include the estimation of IMU error and Kalman Filter covariance matrices using AI algorithms such as Adaptive Network Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) or Deep Learning [37], [40], [57].

C. PERCEPTION

The development of perception algorithms is essential for gaining environmental awareness and, thus, for correctly interpreting the status of the surrounding vehicles and road users. The literature on perception algorithms is extensive, and these algorithms are considered an active field of research. However, despite this, these algorithms are also subject to failures and inaccuracies. The literature on fault tolerance in CAVs contains some works that identify the problem of **Perception malfunction** and propose solutions outside the perception module to reduce its effect [34], [62], [63], [66]–[69]. Although they are not considered failures but functional insufficiencies, **Surrounding vehicle position uncertainty** [70], [71] and **Unpredicted trajectory** [72], [73] may contribute to the occurrence of unsafe situations. Although the majority of works address this problem within the context of the decision-making and planning modules, there are some works addressing these topics with an AI-based approach in the perception module. **AI-based perception failure prediction** has received recent research interest, with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for introspecting object detectors and predict false negatives [67], or to predict failures based on sequences of images [74]. Region-based CNNs and LSTM have also been used to predict failures based on the results of the object detection modules [68], as well as Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based architectures [69]. **AI-based perception reconfiguration** has also been explored to dynamically adapt the fusion algorithms and reduce the influence of faulty sensors or

TABLE 1. Categorization of Automated Driving System Failures, Functional Insufficiencies and Handling Strategies.

Group	Description	Terminology	Type	Related works			
				FO	FD	FS	U
Sensors	General failures in sensors used in CAVs.	Sensor error detection	S	[25]–[28]	[29], [30]	[29]	[31]–[36]
		Sensor isolation	S	[25], [27]	-	[34]	-
		Sensor correction	S	-	[37]	-	[38]–[40]
Ego vehicle localization	Failures and degradation of performances in localization systems, including inaccuracies in the localization algorithms and handling strategies to reduce their impact.	GNSS fault	C	[25], [27], [41]–[48]	[29], [37], [49]–[51]	[29], [52]–[56]	[40], [57]–[60]
		LiDAR localization fault	C	[27], [48]	[29]	[29], [55]	[61]
		Data fusion fault	C	[25]	-	-	-
		Localization sources fusion	S	[41], [43]–[48], [55], [61]	-	-	[59], [60]
		Localization source switch	S	-	[29], [49]–[51]	[29], [53]	-
		AI-based odometry	S	-	[37]	-	[40], [57]
Perception	Deficiencies and malfunctions in environment recognition algorithms, leading to incomplete or incorrect scene understanding and prediction.	Perception malfunction	C	-	-	[62], [63]	[34], [64]–[69]
		Surrounding vehicle position uncertainty	C	[70]	-	-	[71]
		Unpredicted trajectory	C	[72]	-	[73]	-
		AI-based perception failure prediction	S	-	-	-	[67]–[69], [74]
		AI-based perception reconfiguration	S	-	-	-	[66]
Decision / Planning	Dangerous situations generated by erroneous path planning outcomes and strategies at the decision and path planning level to overcome potentially hazardous situations originated from the misbehavior of this or previous groups.	Planning fault	C	[75]	-	[56], [76]–[79]	[80]–[82]
		Backup trajectory provision	S	-	-	[53], [56], [78], [79], [83]–[87]	[80], [81], [88]
		Search-based motion planning	S	-	-	[89]	-
		Time to Collision-based speed profile	S	-	-	[90]	[56]
		Trajectory verification	S	-	-	[52], [54], [73]	-
		Channel arbitration	S	[72], [91]	-	[92]	[93]
		Tactical level fault-tolerance	S	-	-	[94]	[56]
		Transition to Adaptive Cruise Control	S	-	[95]	-	[96]
		AI-based trajectory failure prediction	S	-	-	-	[74], [82], [97], [98]
Control	Advanced controllers to ensure secure operation when encountering faults from other groups.	Model Predictive Control	S	[75]	-	[62], [63], [94]	[71], [99], [100]
		Fault-tolerant control (FTC)	S	[26], [28], [101]–[103]	[30], [104]	[85], [105], [106]	[99], [107]
		AI-enhanced FTC	S	[101], [102]	-	-	-
Communication	Communication malfunctions and solutions based on connectivity for failures and functional insufficiencies of other groups.	Remote driving latency	C	-	-	-	[88], [108]–[111]
		V2X network failure	C	-	[95], [112]–[114]	-	[115], [116]
		Cyberattacks	C	-	[95], [117]	-	[96], [117]–[130]
		Remote driving	S	-	-	-	[131]–[134]
		Infrastructure support	S	-	-	[78]	[135]
Driver-Vehicle Interaction	Strategies that propose interaction between the driver and vehicle to compensate for system failures.	Shared control	S	-	-	[76], [77]	[108]
		Partial automation	S	-	-	-	[136]–[141]
		Driver readiness	S	-	-	-	[138], [140], [141]
		Human-Machine Interface	S	-	-	-	[109], [111], [138]
Vehicle	Failures in the mechanical and electrical parts of the vehicle (e.g., tire blowouts and electric motor failures) and prevention measures based on system redundancy.	Mechanical failures	C	-	-	[85], [92], [105]	[107], [142], [143]
		Electrical and electronic failures	C	[28], [101], [102], [144]	[104]	[92], [94], [105], [106], [145], [146]	[99], [100], [147]–[150]
		Redundancy	S	-	-	-	[148], [149], [151]
		AI-based fault detection	S	-	-	-	[36], [142], [143], [150]

Notes: FD = Fail-Degraded; FO = Fail-Operational; FS = Fail-Safe; U = Unclassified; C = Cause; S = Strategy

perception algorithms using the Aggregate View Object Detection (AVOD) architecture [66].

D. DECISION/PLANNING

CAVs require a robust decision module capable of reacting to the status of the environment and planning the most suitable route to navigate through it. Studies have been proposed in this regard, leveraging the capabilities, and it remains an active field of research. From the perspective of fault tolerance, this module is susceptible to its failures, as well as to those failures or functional insufficiencies inherited by other modules.

The principal cause of potentially dangerous operation generated by this module is a **Planning fault** [75]–[82]. The fault can be caused by several factors, including challenging scenarios, the optimization of the control points, or discrepancies between the driver's intention and the desired outcome in shared control applications.

Conversely, a multitude of studies have demonstrated the significance of decision and path-planning algorithms in ensuring the handling of failures or functional insufficiencies throughout the control architecture. Among the most extensively studied approaches is a strategy known as **Backup trajectory provision** [53], [56], [78]–[81], [83]–[88], which provides an alternative trajectory that is either calculated offline or online and brings the vehicle to a safe and stopped condition when the safety-relevant cause is manifested, usually related to the ego vehicle localization or environmental perception. By contrast, other works integrate the minimal risk maneuver planning into the nominal planner using a **Search-based motion planning** [89]. If the capacity to monitor the environment is constrained, some approaches adopt a **TTC-based speed profile**, assuming the most dangerous possible maneuvers by the surrounding vehicles [56], [90]. Another approach evidenced in the literature is formal methods for **Trajectory verification** [52], [54], [73]. These studies show the potential of verifying the calculated trajectory over a specified time horizon.

On the decision level, there is a tendency in the literature to establish a **Channel arbitration** between different, independent but redundant architectures [72], [91]–[93]. This approach offers the advantage of avoiding common cause failures or insufficiencies that would affect similarly simply redundant architectures. Finally, some works propose a **Tactical level fault-tolerance**, which decides how to respond to a variety of failures using approaches such as Finite State Machines (FSM) or optimization-based management algorithms [56], [94]. Furthermore, in case of failure of cooperative driving architectures, some works propose the **Transition to Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC)** as the handling strategy, although it increases the required minimal inter-vehicle distance [95], [96].

Finally, there has been research interest in the trajectory failure prediction using AI. As such, **AI-based trajectory failure prediction** has been researched with techniques such

as Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) trained on previous sets of trajectories [82]. LSTM have also been used to predict future trajectory failures based on vehicle state information such as speed, acceleration or angular speed [74], [98]. Similar inputs have been employed in combination with Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to predict these trajectory failures [97].

E. CONTROL

Strategies that target the control module as the contention element are common in the literature to manage failures in other modules. The diverse forms of **Fault-tolerant control (FTC)** and their application to the different system failures, including mechanical ones, are currently being studied [26], [28], [30], [85], [99], [101]–[103], [105], [107], with approaches based on Lyapunov theory or control allocation in case of over-actuated systems (e.g., steering applying different torque to each wheel). Nevertheless, the most widely found approach is the **Model Predictive Control** [62], [63], [71], [75], [94], [99], [100]. These studies explore the capability of this controller to consider uncertainties and constraints related to the vehicle and the environment or even a possible transition of control to a human driver. **AI-enhanced FTC** has also been explored using techniques such as RL [101] or Neural Networks (NN) [102] to overcome actuator faults. However, most of the literature of AI-enhanced FTC belongs to other domains such as Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAV).

F. COMMUNICATION

The communication capabilities enhance the possibilities of an automated vehicle and are, therefore, promising. In this regard, there is a large body of literature and ongoing studies focusing on maximizing the potential with applications such as enhanced and cooperative perception or even decentralized decision-making. From a hazard management perspective, the communication capability introduces both failure-handling possibilities and threats. Besides, the cooperative framework allows the extension of the terms *Minimal Risk Manoeuvre* and *Minimal Risk Conditions* (e.g., a vehicle suffering from a perception failure could inform the surrounding vehicles, which could avoid getting close to the compromised vehicle) [155].

The **Remote driving**, also known as **teleoperation**, is seen as a possible fallback strategy where the vehicle control is transferred to a remote operator who manually brings the vehicle to a safe state [131]–[134]. On the other hand, the reliability and dependability of the communication is critical. A common problem in this control architecture is the **Remote driving latency**, which has been identified and investigated as a potential point of failure in several contributions [88], [108]–[111].

Furthermore, CAVs are also exposed to the threat of **cyberattacks**. The ability of safely responding to these cybersecurity risks plays a critical role in ensuring fault

tolerance. Two primary concerns in the context of CAVs are gaining access to the control layer of the vehicle and the loss of anonymity. If an attacker gains access to the vehicle layer, they may be able to manipulate the vehicle's movements, posing a significant risk to the safety of the occupants and other road users. The loss of anonymity, on the other hand, can lead to the disclosure of sensitive information about the vehicle's occupants, their location, and their travel patterns [95], [96], [119].

These attacks mainly target the sensors and the communication. At the sensor level, the feasibility of jamming attacks to GNSS or to a LiDAR is considered high [118]. This attack consists on the generation of intentional interferences targeted at "blinding" the sensor with noise [11]. This noise can be directed to the receiver's antenna, in case of the GNSS, or to LiDAR beams [58], [118]. Another feasible attack targeted to the GNSS is known as spoofing, which consists on the false replication of GNSS signals to produce a localization failure. This attack is considered more dangerous since it is more difficult to detect [11]. At the communication level, the attack types include sybil attacks, replay attacks, Man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. Sybil attacks consist on the creation of many fake identities in the communication network that disrupt the network through the exchange of fake messages. In replay attacks, an adversary records and retransmits valid messages to deceive the vehicle's control system. MITM attacks involve an adversary intercepting and modifying V2X communications. Finally, DoS attacks overwhelm the vehicle's communication systems, rendering them unable to function correctly [124].

There are several defense mechanisms to protect CAVs against these threats, which can be classified in encryption based methods, intrusion detection systems (IDS) and authentication based defense [124]. The encryption based methods include cryptographic algorithms, which can be used to protect data from unauthorized access and secure the communication [124]–[130]. The IDS are designed to detect and alert on potential security threats in real-time, monitoring network traffic, system logs or sensor data. Some of the most recent IDS involve Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) [120], LSTM neural networks [117], [123], and simple Neural Networks in combination with Fuzzy Logic [121]. Finally, the authentication ensures that only authorized entities can access the vehicle's systems and data [124], [156].

Although cooperative driving brings benefits such as platooning, Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (CACC) or cooperative perception, it depends on the reliability of the V2X. The impact of a **V2X network failure** could be critical in CACC, as studied in [95], [112], [115], [116].

Finally, some works concur in the use of **Infrastructure support** to assist in the calculation execution of minimal risk manoeuvres or to support the transition of control if

the driver takes too long to react to a takeover request [78], [135].

G. DRIVER-VEHICLE INTERACTION

Although the capabilities and robustness of CAVs have indeed undertaken an enormous enhancement during the last couple of years, the driver is still frequently used as the fallback or mitigation mechanism, i.e., a **partial automation** [136]–[141]. Some works also introduce **Shared control**, in which the driver and the automated system share control of the vehicle simultaneously, to bridge the possible discrepancies between the vehicle motion planning and the behavior desired by the driver [76], [77], [108].

As specified in the SAE J3016 [4], the fallback mechanism can rely on the driver to perform the driving task. Nonetheless, the attention paid to the driving task by the driver is reduced after long periods of continuous automated driving [157]. Therefore, another current trend is to monitor the **Driver readiness** to decide whether he can undertake the vehicle control in case of a failure that would require a fallback strategy [138], [140], [141]. Finally, other studies suggest the use of a **Human-Machine Interface (HMI)** to help the driver (On-board or remote) mitigate possible failures [109], [111], [138].

H. VEHICLE

Apart from the failures and functional insufficiencies specific to the automation of the vehicle, a CAV is also exposed to the common threats that a conventional vehicle can suffer. These possible failures include **Mechanical failures** such as tire punctures or blowouts or a mechanical failure of the steering system [85], [92], [105], [107], [142], [143]. Besides, other vehicle-related failures are the **Electrical and electronic failures** in actuators or electronic components [28], [36], [92], [94], [99]–[102], [105], [106], [144]–[150].

The most explored and well-known strategy for mitigating vehicle failures is the **Redundancy** at the component level (e.g., Electronic Control Units and actuators) [148], [149] or at the functionality level (e.g cross-actuator functional redundancy) [144]. Nevertheless, other studies approach the problem from a control perspective, as already outlined in the Subsection E. In the recent years, some studies have pointed towards the electrical and mechanical **AI-based fault detection**, using model-based techniques such as SVM (Support Vector Machine) [143], [150] instead of conventional observers, or adaptive denoising residual networks [142].

IV. DEGRADATION AND OPERATIONAL STRATEGIES

The occurrence of failures and functional insufficiencies does not always necessitate a fallback maneuver that brings the vehicle to a safe and stopped condition. Instead, a fault-tolerant strategy that continues the operation may be available. As summarised in Section II, the vehicle may continue driving with the same capabilities if it is Fail-

Operational. In the event that the vehicle requires a reduction in its operational capabilities (e.g., maximum speed, ODD) in order to continue functioning, it is classified as Fail-Degraded.

The most relevant degradation and operational approaches found in the literature are gathered in Table 2. The contributions are classified by the affected module, the fault or functional insufficiency, the handling strategy, the validation environment, and the ODD.

A. ACQUISITION AND PERCEPTION

The literature contains several contributions that address issues related to the acquisition and perception modules. In particular, there are several papers that propose specific countermeasures for the well-known GNSS outages [25], [27], [29], [37], [44]–[48], [50]. The work by Bader *et al.* presents a fault-tolerant data fusion architecture applied to localization and studies how to overcome a single failure in the odometry sensor or GNSS. The authors suggest two independent localization pipelines, each of them containing sensors (which differ between the two pipelines) and a Kalman filter. If the difference in the output of the Kalman filters exceeds a specified threshold, the occurrence of an error is detected. The faulty component is then identified by comparing the output of the prediction and the correction steps with the dual of the other Kalman filter and the residual values from the fusion. The contribution is evaluated with real-world recorded data from a vehicle driving on a test track, including straights and roundabouts. Using their methodology, the fail-operational localization is ensured in the event of a single point of failure [25].

In the work presented by Parra Alonso *et al.*, a GNSS insufficiency or blackout is addressed through visual odometry with the help of a map-matching technique to correct the cumulative errors. The efficacy of the proposed methodology is evaluated in a real-world urban scenario, with vehicle speeds up to 50 km/h and illumination changes. They state to obtain a mean distance error below 1.5% over a traveled distance of more than 7 km. Although the percentage is promising, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is only shown at the end runs of 500 m on average, which is of the order of a few meters. Consequently, it is unclear whether their algorithm could be used in a CAV during a limited GNSS failure or is, by contrast, restricted to the use in Advanced Driving Assistance Systems (ADAS) [50].

The contribution of Brossard *et al.* to handle a GNSS outage is an IMU-based dead-reckoning that uses an EKF whose covariance noise parameters are dynamically adapted through a CNN. The principal advantage of the contribution is the localization achieved without the necessity for additional sensors. The proposed method is trained and evaluated using sequences of the KITTI dataset [159], with training and validation split accordingly. The method achieves an average 1.1% translational error on drives of about 1 km, using only an IMU, and shows a similar performance during shorter

lengths. In conclusion, the contribution could be classified as Fail-Degraded, provided that the GNSS outage is limited in duration [37].

The use of the different variants of the Kalman filter for sensor fusion is a recurrent approach to overcome GNSS outages [44], [46]–[48]. In the work presented by Meng *et al.*, a UKF fuses GNSS measurements with IMU measurements and the encoder readings. Afterward, the lateral error produced by the sensor inaccuracies is corrected through the comparison of curb measurements made by a LiDAR and map information. Besides, the authors propose a rule-based automatic detector of GNSS performance degradation. The algorithm is evaluated in a real environment, and the authors claim to maintain a maximum lateral error below 1.2 m. Nevertheless, the documented validation experiments are limited, and further testing would be beneficial to evaluate the capability of being used in a CAV [44].

The work made by Min *et al.* addresses the issue of GNSS signal degradation through the fusion of Visual SLAM, IMU measurements, and GNSS in an EKF. Besides, this approach employs an interacting multiple-model filter, which combines and weights a kinematic and a dynamic vehicle model. The authors evaluate their approach using sequences from the KITTI dataset, obtaining an RMSE of approximately 1 m, but the magnitude of the GNSS degradation remains unclear. Furthermore, the algorithm was evaluated in a real-world environment, where conditions prone to GNSS degradations, such as tunnels and indoor parking, were present. The results indicated an RMSE of approximately 1.5 m, which represents an improvement over the 4.5 m achieved by solely utilizing the GNSS and IMU measurements [47].

In their study, Matute *et al.* present an approach designed for use in rural forested environments. They propose GNSS and LiDAR map-matching localization fusion based on an EKF, with a weighted gate approach based on the Mahalanobis gates to filter outliers in the observations when the covariance information from the GNSS or the LiDAR localization is unavailable. The proposed algorithm was evaluated at a maximum speed of 40 km/h in a real-world rural environment that exhibited unmapped zones, which constrained the use of LiDAR localization, as well as zones with frequent GNSS outages. The results yielded an RMSE of 0.15 m, with a maximum of 0.48 m for the positioning error, and an RMSE of 1.44° with a maximum of 11.77° for the angular error. This demonstrates the capability to operate after the denial of one of the two localization sources [48].

Wan *et al.* propose a method for overcoming GNSS outages and LiDAR localization failures. This method involves the use of an error-state Kalman filter to fuse GNSS, map-matching LiDAR localization, and IMU measurements. It also addresses the issue of transmission and computation delay. The system was tested in real-world scenarios, including weak GNSS zones such as tunnels or garages. The authors assert that the proposed system is capable of achieving a localization accuracy of less than 0.1 m, with a

TABLE 2. Degradation / Operational approaches classified by affected groups.

Group	Fault / Functional Insufficiency	Handling Strategy	Validation	ODD	Work	
Acquisition, Localization and Perception	Odometry sensor failure	Fault detection, identification and isolation through similar sensor output comparison and data fusion	Real (recorded data)	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Straight lane, roundabout Speed: N/A	Bader <i>et al.</i> [25] (2017)	
		Visual Odometry and map matching techniques	Real	Road type: Urban Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: 50 km/h	Parra Alonso <i>et al.</i> [50] (2012)	
		Deep learning-based dynamic adaptation of covariance noise parameters of a Kalman Filter	Real (dataset)	Road type: Urban, Highway Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: N/A	Brossard <i>et al.</i> [37] (2020)	
	GNSS Outage	Kalman Filter-based sensor fusion		Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: N/A	Meng <i>et al.</i> [44] (2017)
				Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 45-55 km/h	Min <i>et al.</i> [47] (2019)
				Real	Road type: Rural road Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 40 km/h	Matute <i>et al.</i> [48] (2023)
		Kalman Filter-based fault detection and isolation		Real	Road type: Urban, tunnel Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: N/A	Wan <i>et al.</i> [46] (2018)
				Real	Road type: Highway Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: 80 km/h	Mori <i>et al.</i> [27] (2019)
				Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Straight lane, roundabout Speed: N/A	Bader <i>et al.</i> [25] (2017)
				Real	Road type: Urban, Highway Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: 60 km/h	Suhr <i>et al.</i> [45] (2017)
	Reconfigurable localization architecture	Virtual	Road type: Urban Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: N/A km/h	Viana <i>et al.</i> [29] (2022)		
	LiDAR localization failure	Kalman Filter-based sensor fusion	Real	Road type: Rural road Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 40 km/h	Matute <i>et al.</i> [48] (2023)	
			Virtual	Road type: Highway Scenarios: Open traffic Speed: 80 km/h	Mori <i>et al.</i> [27] (2019)	
	Incorrect detection and prediction	Arbitration method in multi-channel architecture to avoid functional insufficiencies	Virtual	Road type: Urban Scenarios: Missed, false detection Speed: 0-50 km/h	Hanselaar <i>et al.</i> [91] (2022)	
Decision and Control	Probability of not achieving safety specifications	Risk probability and severity aware motion planning	Real (dataset)	CommonRoad USA_US101-11_4_T-1:2018 [158]	Nyberg <i>et al.</i> [70] (2021)	
	Surroundings uncertainty	Uncertainty propagation and MPC-based motion planning considering roll-over risk	Hardware-in-the-loop	Road type: Highway Scenarios: Cut-in, merging Speed: 72-108 km/h	Tang <i>et al.</i> [71] (2022)	
	Speed sensor failure	Longitudinal control based on a sensor failure observer and a state feedback integral controller	Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 0-120 km/h	Boukhari <i>et al.</i> [26] (2019)	
	Communication failure in CACC	Degradation to bigger inter-vehicle distances or ACC	Virtual	Road type: Highway Scenarios: Platooning Speed: 0-100 km/h	Segata <i>et al.</i> [95] (2023)	
	Yaw-rate sensor fault	Switching between a set of controllers with different sensor inputs	Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 0-20 km/h	Venkita <i>et al.</i> [28] (2020)	
	On-board electric motor fault	Torque redistribution among the remaining motors	Real	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Simple circuit Speed: 0-20 km/h	Venkita <i>et al.</i> [28] (2020)	
			Virtual	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Lane change Speed: 0-60 km/h	Stolte <i>et al.</i> [99] (2023)	
Steering motor fault	Steering through the application of different wheel torques	Virtual	Road type: Test track Scenarios: Lane change, curve path Speed: 0-60 km/h	Chen <i>et al.</i> [100] (2021)		

maximum error of 0.26 m. While the paper does not provide information about the angular error, the contribution appears to be an appropriate solution for overcoming GNSS outages, provided that the LiDAR localization is available [46].

In Mori *et al.*, the authors propose a sensor failure detection and isolation method with an adaptive Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF). Their contribution consists of a state and measurement prediction, a sensor fault detection and isolation based on Hotelling's T^2 statistics, and a measurement noise update based on Student's t-distribution. The proposed contribution is validated in the real world using GNSS data in a highway scenario. It is claimed that the accuracy is increased during temporal GNSS outages compared to other dead-reckoning approaches, with localization errors of around 1.5 meters at the end of 30 seconds of GNSS outage. Furthermore, it is asserted that anomalies can be anticipated before the GNSS receiver outputs a decrement in reliability [27].

A completely different approach is proposed by Suhr *et al.*. Instead of using a Kalman filter-based approach to circumvent GNSS outages, the authors propose a particle filter to fuse GNSS, IMU, odometry, a front camera, and a digital map. The proposed algorithm was tested in drives of more than 8 km along an urban environment, including weak GNSS zones such as tunnels. The authors claim to achieve a mean error between 1 and 1.7 m. The results appear promising, but the evolution of the error during the GNSS outages is not specified. Thus, further information about the performance in these situations would be required to determine whether this method can be used in CAVs or is restricted to ADAS [45].

The authors of Viana *et al.* proposed a reconfigurable localization framework that is capable of detecting sensor failures and reconfiguring the system through the combination of fusion algorithms and decision strategies. The framework is based on a hierarchical structure comprising three levels. Each level employs a different localization approach, namely relative localization, relative localization plus road-matching, and global localization. Additionally, an error detection block is incorporated. The most suitable level is selected based on the available sensors. Moreover, a fallback maneuver can be executed in the event of unreliable localization (analyzed in Section V). The proposed algorithm was evaluated using the Carla Simulator, where multiple failures and recoveries were injected. The authors assert that the lateral mean error is below 0.5 m, and the longitudinal mean error is within the range of 1 to 3 m at the end of the drive [29].

In their study, Hanselaar *et al.* present an approach to address more generic functional insufficiencies related to the perception system, including localization, object detection, and motion prediction. The authors propose the concept of a *safety shell*, which consists of a multi-channel architecture with an arbitrary number of independent heterogeneous channels. Provided that at least one of the channels correctly

perceives the environmental situation, the authors propose an arbitration strategy that considers risk calculations and avoids constant channel switching. The proposed methodology is validated through the use of simulations representing a variety of use cases, such as missing and false positive detection and predicted collision [91].

B. DECISION AND CONTROL

Another prevalent trend identified in the literature contains the studies that address failures and functional insufficiencies from a decision and control perspective. In contrast to the strategies that rely on the acquisition and perception modules, these studies address a more diverse range of issues [26], [28], [70], [71], [95], [99], [100].

In their study, Nyberg *et al.* address the risk of violating a safety specification considering all uncertainties in the state estimates. The authors put forth a risk measure for estimating the probability and expected severity of the safety violation. This is based on a random variable that describes the severity of violating the safety constraint, given by an associated severity function. The authors evaluate the risk measure with the USA_US101-11_4_T-1:2018 scenario from CommonRoad [158] and illustrate the change of risk over time. The simulations demonstrate the advantages of incorporating this risk measurement into the motion planner, which translates into a reduction of overall risk [70].

Tang *et al.* propose a local motion planner that considers the uncertainty of surrounding vehicles while considering the risk of rollover. The authors employ an EKF to propagate the uncertainty of surrounding vehicles' positions and an MPC as the motion planner, which incorporates the risk of rollover. Moreover, the vehicle model is based on a four-degree-of-freedom dynamic model. The proposed methodology was evaluated in a Hardware-in-the-Loop environment in two obstacle-avoidance use cases: Cut-in and merging. The results show an improvement in the risk of rollover and in the proposed safety index [71].

The work made by Boukhari *et al.* addresses the issue of handling additive faults in the speed sensor in the longitudinal control in a CACC scheme. The authors present a fault-tolerant control scheme based on a state feedback integral controller and fault estimation observers to compensate for the sensor faults. Furthermore, the authors validate their proposal in a real-world environment, with speeds up to 120 m/h, emulating additive faults in the sensed speed. The results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed estimation methodology for additive faults, which enables more reliable control [26].

Segata *et al.* examine the degradation mechanisms that enable the continued operation of a platoon of vehicles in the event of a communication failure. The authors propose a tactical level fault tolerance through an FSM, which includes states such as bigger inter-vehicle distances or even the degradation from CACC to ACC for the worst cases. Additionally, the authors propose a progressive inter-vehicle

distance modification through rate of change limitation. The performance is evaluated in simulation and demonstrates improvements in the necessary acceleration and distances for single and multiple vehicle failure compared to a direct transition to ACC [95].

Other approaches examine the suitability of the control and decision modules for addressing failures at a vehicle level. One of these studies, proposed by Venkita *et al.*, proposes a fault-tolerant lateral controller that can accommodate a yaw rate sensor fault by switching to a backup controller that is calibrated to operate independently of the yaw rate measurement. Moreover, the authors incorporate a methodology for detecting faults through residual evaluation. To prevent undesirable transitions following the controller switch, the authors also suggest implementing an arbitration law between them. Furthermore, the authors put forth a strategy to surmount failures in a malfunctioning motor (assuming an all-wheel drive configuration, thus rendering the lateral dynamics over-actuated). In this case, the authors propose a torque redistribution between the available motors. The contribution is evaluated in a real-world configuration at low speeds, approximately 20 km/h. Additionally, the faults are artificially injected. The documented results demonstrate that the proposed architecture is capable of maintaining the desired trajectory during a lane change maneuver [28].

The work by Stolte *et al.* is also directed toward mechanical failures, including actuator degradations and failures, as well as tire blowouts. The authors assume the use of vehicles featuring four-wheel individual steering, drive, and brake actuators, thus, they are over-actuated. The proposed approach is the use of an MPC and reconfiguration of its constraints, weight, and prediction model. The efficacy of the proposed algorithm is evaluated in a vehicle dynamics simulator across two different trajectories, a lane change and a decelerating lane change. The results show that the approach can handle these degradation and failures, although it is subject to certain limitations. Given the complexity of the simulated dynamics, a real-world validation would be beneficial to examine whether the approach could be used in a real vehicle. However, the results are promising, at least, for being able to perform a fallback maneuver [99].

A similar approach is proposed by Chen *et al.* The authors present a solution to steering motor faults in vehicles featuring four-wheel individual motors based on the redistribution of torque among the motors. The proposed control architecture is based on an MPC to obtain the expected front-wheel steering angle, and a non-singular terminal sliding mode controller is employed to track it by differential steering using the wheel motors. The algorithm is validated in simulation using Carsim and Simulink, where the maneuvers of a circular path and a lane change are analyzed. The results presented by the authors indicate an effective tracking of the required trajectory, which could allow this strategy to be used in a degradation mode [100].

V. FALLBACK STRATEGIES

In the event of a system failure or functional insufficiency, the most appropriate response is sometimes to cease the nominal operation and transition to a minimal risk condition through the execution of a fallback maneuver. As previously outlined in Section II, the ADS is required to bring the vehicle to a safe state deliberately and consciously.

Table 3 compiles the most relevant contributions that implement fallback maneuvers in response to diverse failures. The contributions are classified according to the module that is affected by the failure, the nature of the failure, the fallback maneuver, the ODD, the approach, and the testing environment.

A. PERCEPTION

A malfunction in the perception system can result in hazardous circumstances for both the ego vehicle and the road users. In this regard, several contributions have been made that propose fallback strategies for these failures [63], [83], [89], [90].

In the event of a generic frontal detection sensor failure in a highway scenario, Xue *et al.* propose a fallback strategy that involves bringing the vehicle to a stop in a parking zone. The parking zone is not always available immediately, thus, it may be necessary to continue driving temporarily. The authors generate virtual vehicles in the last known position of the surrounding vehicles. They then assume aggressive, but legal, movements against the ego vehicle. The approach was evaluated in simulation in two highway scenarios, where the authors claim that the vehicle was capable of executing the fallback maneuver while maintaining a safe spacing to the surrounding vehicles [63].

In their study, Emzivat *et al.* propose a fallback strategy to address complete unreliability in the detection module, with the added complexity that the stop in the current lane is prohibited and dangerous, and the vehicle must reach the end of the road. The authors propose a solution based on the replacement of missing objects with ghost objects, and a TTC-based speed profile that depends on the visibility of the road is employed. The authors evaluate the algorithm in simulation and conclude that it reduces the number of collisions and close calls in the event of perception failure [90].

In Tong *et al.*, the authors propose a solution to address perception failures by extending a nominal directed-graph map with a backup search-based motion planner for minimal risk maneuvers. The authors employ a monitoring device for supervising the health of the sensors and, when necessary, initiate the backup search graph, rather than continuously computing the backup trajectory. This approach reduces the system's complexity by limiting the computational load. Besides, the proposed backup planner is capable of stopping the vehicle on the shoulder, when available, or on the road. The authors evaluate the proposed algorithm in a simulation environment using the Carla Simulator, where they demon-

TABLE 3. DDT Fallback Strategies in Automated Vehicles classified by affected group.

Group	Failure	Fallback	ODD	Approach	Testing	Work
Perception	Frontal detection	Roadside parking	Road type: Highway Speed: 50-100 km/h Objects: Surroundings	Missing vehicles are replaced with virtual lead vehicles	Virtual B-class Hatchback Simulink / Carsim	Xue <i>et al.</i> [63] (2018)
		Remove vehicle from active lane of traffic	Road type: Highway Speed: 0-70 km/h Objects: Lead, follow	Adjust speed to keep safe distance to ghost vehicles	Virtual ADS-EV SCANeR studio	Emzivat <i>et al.</i> [90] (2017)
	360° detection	Roadside parking	Road type: Urban Speed: 0-47 km/h Objects: Surroundings	Directed graph-map for normal driving conditions extension	Virtual ADS-EV VIFWare / Carla [160]	Tong <i>et al.</i> [89] (2022)
		Slowly stop in shoulder or in lane	Road type: Urban Speed: 0-00 km/h Objects: Lead	Real-time safe stop trajectory planning from precomputed OCP	Virtual KTH RCV ROS / Gazebo	Svensson <i>et al.</i> [83] (2018)
Localization	Localization failure	Roadside parking	Road type: Urban Speed: 0-18 km/h Objects: Roadside	A virtual positioning sensor provides an indirect localization	Virtual Electric bus Simulink / Dynacar [161]	Matute <i>et al.</i> [53] (2020)
			Road type: Highway Speed: 0-61 km/h Objects: No	Change lane immediately after failure and stop	Virtual ADS-EV Simulink / Carsim	Yu <i>et al.</i> [56] (2019)
		Road type: Urban Speed: N/A Objects: No	Slow stop in the lane	Virtual Tesla 3 Simulink / Carla [160]	Viana <i>et al.</i> [29] (2022)	
	Emergency stop	Road type: Urban Speed: N/A Objects: No	Swiftly stop the vehicle in lane	Not specified KTH RCV	Krook <i>et al.</i> [54] (2020)	
		Road type: Highway Speed: 120 km/h Objects: No	Dead reckoning provides localization during safe stop	Real Volvo XC90	Jonasson <i>et al.</i> [55] (2020)	
Decision	Loss path redundancy	Continue driving to safe location	Road type: Highway Speed: 0-61 km/h Objects: No	Reduce speed, keep driving to safe location and stop	Virtual ADS-EV Simulink / Carsim	Yu <i>et al.</i> [56] (2019)
		Shared control	Road type: Highway Speed: 44-92 km/h Objects: Surroundings	Shared control-based transition to minimal risk condition	Virtual ADS-EV Simulink / Carsim	Xue <i>et al.</i> [77] (2023)
	Planning failure	Road type: Urban Speed: 0-7.2 km/h Objects: Roadside	Infrastructure provides backup fallback trajectory	Virtual/Real BMW active hybrid 3 PreScan / HiL	Pechinger <i>et al.</i> [78] (2020)	
		Road type: Highway Speed: 50-72 km/h Objects: Surroundings	Precomputed emergency backup trajectory	Virtual Dynamic bicycle model	Magdici <i>et al.</i> [84] (2016)	
	Unexpected trajectory of surrounding vehicles	Roadside parking	Road type: Urban Speed: 0-28 km/h Objects: Surroundings	Infinite-horizon verification of fail-safe trajectory	Real BMW 7-series	Pek <i>et al.</i> [73] (2021)
Actuation	Under-steering	Roadside parking	Road type: Highway Speed: 0-100 km/h Objects: Lead, follow	Reconfigure NMPC after failure and reach a safe state	Virtual Particle model	Lodder <i>et al.</i> [94] (2023)
			Road type: Highway Speed: 0-70 km/h Objects: No	Redistribute steering action into differential braking	Virtual Renault Scenic CarMaker Virtual Two track model	Khelladi <i>et al.</i> [105] (2020) Boudali <i>et al.</i> [92] (2018)
	Tire blowout	Continue driving to safe location	Road type: Highway Speed: 0-108 km/h Objects: Lead	Primary auxiliary brake wheel braking maneuver	Virtual Simulink / Carsim	Yue <i>et al.</i> [85] (2019)

strate that the method is capable of correctly searching for a suitable backup trajectory, with particular attention paid to the computational load that it requires, which meets the needs of the control period [89].

Svensson *et al.* studied the suitability of optimal control and precomputed stopped trajectories in the task of safe stop trajectory planning. The authors do not explicitly indicate the failure, but correct localization, decision, and actuation modules are assumed. The selected strategy is to gradually decelerate on the shoulder, when available, or in the lane. The evaluation was conducted in simulation at low speeds, where the authors observed that the precomputed trajectories replicated the behavior of the optimal control while maintaining an adequate runtime performance [83].

B. LOCALIZATION

Failures in the localization module can result in operational risks for a CAV, potentially necessitating the execution of a fallback maneuver to end the operation. This issue has been identified and addressed in various contributions to the literature [29], [53]–[56].

The authors of Matute *et al.* address the issue of localization failure through the use of a virtual sensor based on an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF). This virtual sensor employs the odometry, the IMU measurements, and the cornering stiffness of the vehicle to provide indirect localization. Furthermore, the cornering stiffness is interpolated from a database with the values of velocity and front-wheel angle. The fallback maneuver consists of a roadside parking on the next available shoulder, thus, the system is designed in a way that it may continue driving for a limited time until a shoulder is available. The algorithm was evaluated in a multi-body vehicle dynamics simulator using an electric bus, where they demonstrated to effectively reduce the localization error, allowing for the correct execution of the designed fallback maneuver [53].

Yu *et al.* put forth a scenario-based fallback strategy. Their approach entails a variety of maneuvers, including roadside parking and stopping in the lane, contingent on the severity and nature of the failure. Furthermore, the fallback maneuvers are designed for failures beyond the localization module, yet the evaluation of the algorithm is conducted in simulation with a GNSS failure. The results demonstrate that the vehicle successfully executes the fallback maneuver. However, there is a paucity of information regarding how the ego-vehicle computes its location after the failure, and the presented simulations are limited. Consequently, the primary contribution is at the conceptual level. [56].

Viana *et al.*, which was analyzed in detail in Section IV, also proposes the use of a fallback maneuver, which consists of a slow stop in the lane, if the relative localization is utilized and the drift cannot be corrected [29].

In Krook *et al.*, the authors address GNSS failures through the activation of a dedicated safe stop trajectory planner, which generates the minimal risk maneuver. The safe stop

trajectory planner is embedded in a tactical planner, which is formally verified using supervisory control theory and reactive synthesis. This constitutes the principal contribution of their study since neither real-world nor simulation tests are documented in the manuscript [54].

The authors of Jonasson *et al.* rely exclusively on proprioceptive sensors, namely an IMU, wheel speed sensors, and a pinion angle sensor, to compute an emergency localization after the main localization sources suffer a complete failure. Thus, the authors study whether performing a *blind* safe stop that relies on dead-reckoning is realistic. Besides the sensors, an EKF including a complex dynamic model is employed. Real data at speeds up to 120 km/h is recorded and used to evaluate the algorithm while executing different maneuvers that assimilate to a safe stop maneuver. The results indicate that the efficacy of the method is highly dependent on the velocity and the maneuver, being suitable for speeds not surpassing 70 km/h, where the error is limited to 0.75 m laterally and 3 m longitudinally [55].

C. DECISION

Another group of fallback strategies is composed of those studies that address failures originating in the decision module [56], [73], [77], [78], [84].

In the event of a failure of the behavioral or motion planner, the authors of Xue *et al.* propose the inclusion of the human as a component of the fallback strategy. Rather than relying exclusively on the human, they propose the incorporation of shared control. Their contribution entails the estimation of the intentions of the driver, the distribution of the driving authority according to his response, and the generation of trajectories with a receding horizon planner aiming for the minimal risk condition. In the event of a discrepancy between the computed trajectory and the driver's intentions, the former is given precedence. The proposed algorithm was evaluated using a simulator with a high-fidelity dynamic vehicle model across a range of scenarios, including abrupt lane changes and hard brakes. The authors posit that the algorithm reduces the accident rate and enhances the likelihood of attaining the minimal risk condition [77].

Pechinger *et al.* assess the viability of an infrastructure-based motion planner to provide a fallback trajectory through V2X communication in the event of a failure of the vehicle motion planner. The vehicle controller then processes the received trajectory and guides the vehicle to the stop position, which is defined as the shoulder. The architecture was analyzed in a Hardware-in-the-Loop environment, where the scenario and the objects are simulated, but the vehicle is driving in reality. The authors conclude that the communication delay is limited to an average of 33 ms and that the vehicle can successfully execute the received trajectories [78].

The authors of Magdici *et al.* present a motion planner that incorporates the calculation of an emergency maneuver, which is designed to bring the vehicle to standstill conditions during nominal operation. In each iteration, the

planner calculates an emergency maneuver that considers the potential future positions of surrounding vehicles within a specified time frame. Upon receiving new measurements, the system assesses whether the nominal optimal trajectory can be calculated. If this is no longer feasible, the previously calculated emergency trajectory is executed. The proposed algorithm is evaluated through numerical simulations using a dataset comprising actual vehicle trajectories [84].

A comparable methodology is employed by Pek *et al.* The authors propose a motion planner that maintains and verifies over an infinite-time horizon a backup fallback maneuver, provided that the surrounding vehicles execute unanticipated but lawful movements. The fallback maneuvers are continuously generated while the ego vehicle is in motion. However, if no new valid trajectory can be generated, the previous fallback maneuver is executed. Moreover, the trajectory is online verified by the integration as constraints of invariably safe sets. The contribution was evaluated with a real test vehicle in simple traffic scenarios and with recorded data in more complex ones. The authors posit that the algorithm is capable of executing the fallback maneuver when necessary while maintaining a style of driving that is not overly conservative [73].

D. ACTUATION

The final set of fallback maneuvers comprises works that address failures in the actuation module. It should be noted that these failures are not necessarily associated with automated driving capabilities. Rather, they may pertain to vehicle failures [85], [92], [94], [105]. In the work by Lodder *et al.*, the authors propose utilizing a nonlinear MPC to safely bring a vehicle traveling in an ACC convoy to a halt in the event of a power steering failure. The failures are modeled and incorporated into the dynamic vehicle model, which is reconfigured after the occurrence of the failure. The effectiveness of the technique was evaluated in simulation, where the authors compared the effects on braking in and out of lane maneuvers. The authors assert that the performance achieved during the fallback maneuver is comparable to that observed before the failure [94].

The studies of Boudali *et al.* and Khelladi *et al.* employ a similar methodology. They endeavor to implement a fallback maneuver that leads to parking on the roadside in the event of a steering system failure. This is achieved by redistributing the steering action into differential braking in an all-wheel drive vehicle. Boudali *et al.* propose a dedicated emergency controller with separated lateral and longitudinal controllers and a management mechanism to circumvent potential conflicts between them. The efficacy of the method was assessed through a simple simulation test, wherein the vehicle demonstrated acceptable execution of the proposed trajectory [92]. Khelladi *et al.* propose, by contrast, a more sophisticated algorithm. The proposed architecture comprises three main components: a reference generation module, a guidance control based on state feedback, and

a control allocation law that adapts the control commands to the available actuators. The performance of this approach was evaluated in simulation using a variety of use cases, and the results demonstrated the algorithm's effectiveness [105].

Tire blowouts are the focus of the study of Yue *et al.* The authors put forth a proposal that includes transitioning to the emergency lane when feasible and the implementation of an emergency braking control system. The emergency brake control designates the opposite of the failed wheel as the primary brake wheel, with the remaining two wheels serving as auxiliary. The primary brake wheel is employed to balance the rolling resistance moment between the left and right wheels and to correct the vehicle's driving directionality, while the auxiliary brake wheels are utilized to stop the vehicle as expediently as possible. The authors evaluated their approach with a high-fidelity dynamics simulator, wherein they assert that the algorithm successfully executed the fallback maneuver [85].

VI. INDUSTRY PERSPECTIVES

While most of the works examined in this review originate from academic institutions, the CAV industry has also embraced the necessity of adopting fault tolerance mechanisms to preserve safety. Most companies operating fleets of robotaxis or introducing Level 3 automated capabilities to their cars have published safety reports. These reports typically provide a high-level overview of the design and functionality of their safety-critical systems, as well as an outline of their validation methodologies. However, these industry reports generally lack the technical depth and detail present in the academic works analyzed in this review, limiting the extent to which their approaches can be scrutinized and compared.

Waymo, a subsidiary of Alphabet, has launched a robotaxi service in several US cities, with a notable emphasis on safety in their operations. Their Safety Report [162] dedicates a page to detailing their fallback mechanisms, which are used to ensure that their robotaxis can transition to a full stop in case of failures. According to the report, Waymo employs a secondary computer running in parallel with the primary system, designed to execute a fallback maneuver upon detecting a failure. This secondary system is capable of performing thousands of real-time checks per second to diagnose faults. Furthermore, they report having implemented a backup redundant inertial localization system, backup steering and braking systems that can manage the actuation independently, backup power systems, redundant and separate communication systems for critical signals, and multiple and redundant collision detection and avoidance systems. They also test and validate these capabilities through a combination of simulation testing, closed-course testing, and public road testing. The simulation testing is used to reproduce challenging situations with different variations. Then, the closed-course tests allow for reproducing multiple scenarios in the real world, but in controlled sce-

narios. Finally, the capabilities are validated on public roads with safety drivers.

Cruise, a company initially focused on robotaxi services, published their Safety Report [163], providing a high-level description of their fault tolerance mechanisms for their experimental robotaxis. Specifically, they outline a five-level degradation framework categorized according to the severity of the failure. These levels comprise Fail Operational capabilities in cases of a benign latent malfunction, Fail Degraded operation with stricter constraints or limitations in cases of tolerated malfunctions, Fail Safe capabilities involving a Fallback maneuver to a safe stop with more severe malfunctions, and quick slowdowns in lane for the total loss of autonomous functionalities. These levels of degradation are aligned with the terms of the international standards. To validate these capabilities, Cruise first utilized simulation testing, followed by closed-course testing where degraded states were injected, and finally, they conducted testing on public roads. Finally, they are tested on public roads. However, in 2025, Cruise was acquired by General Motors, which subsequently announced a shift in strategy, halting the development of robotaxi services and refocusing efforts towards developing automated capabilities for personal vehicles [164].

Mercedes-Benz has developed Level 3 automated driving capabilities, known as DRIVE PILOT, which are being integrated into select models. DRIVE PILOT enables operation in limited Operational Design Domains (ODDs) with speeds of up to 95 km/h on German Autobahns [165]. As a Level 3 system, the driver is expected to remain attentive and prepared to intervene in cases of system failures or exit from the ODD [166]. Nevertheless, the system is capable of executing a fallback maneuver to a safe stop if the driver fails to take control within a specified timeframe.

BMW has also developed Level 3 automated capabilities for personal cars, which are available in the BMW 7 Series and limited to traffic jams ODDs [167]. In their Safety Assessment Report [168], BMW describes how the system alerts and expects the fallback-ready user to take over the vehicle control after an ADS failure or an ODD exit. Provided that the driver is unresponsive, they claim that the ADS executes a fallback maneuver (e.g., stop in the shoulder or the current lane).

Zoox, a subsidiary of Amazon, is currently developing robotaxis and has outlined its approach to fault tolerance in its Safety Report [169]. They claim to incorporate system redundancy to eliminate single points of failure in safety-critical systems, such as batteries and powertrains. Furthermore, they claim to incorporate an advanced monitoring system that can precisely detect fault states across the vehicle hardware, software, and firmware. Specifically, the vehicle may be able to continue operating with limited abilities (Fail Degraded), navigate to a suitable location to stop safely (Fail Safe), or, in extreme cases, execute a rapid emergency stop to prevent an accident.

Motional, a joint venture between the Hyundai Motor Group and Aptiv, is focused on developing technology for robotaxis. In their Voluntary Safety Self-Assessment [170], Motional provides an overview of their fallback systems. The company employs a tier-based classification system to categorize failures according to their criticality and urgency. The most critical failures (e.g., primary control system lost) lead to pull-over maneuvers and, thus, belong to the Fail Safe category. Less critical failures (e.g., loss of sensor, but overlapping coverage available) allow the ride to finish and request maintenance, and hence, can be categorized as Fail Degraded.

In the trucking sector, Aurora has been developing an autonomous trucking solution. Before the incoming initiation of operations, they have released their Driverless Safety Report [171]. They state that to have redundant, separated, and isolated components are required for the critical subsystems. Besides, through a process of health checking, they claim to be able to detect failures and determine their impact. The mitigation strategy consists of a fail-safe pull-over maneuver, with the possibility of driving until designated stop locations to minimize the risk of collisions, depending on the severity of the failure and the road conditions. However, this is still a fail-safe behavior since the goal is still to execute a pull-over maneuver.

Waabi, also in the trucking sector, is preparing the launch of fully driverless trucks. In their Voluntary Safety-Self Assessment report [172], they briefly state that they incorporate fallback strategies as a response to non-nominal conditions and faults.

This section has provided an overview of the publicly available perspectives on fault tolerance from major industry actors. A common thread among these industry leaders is their adoption of an approach centered on system redundancy and health monitoring. Furthermore, all of them claim to have the capability to execute fallback maneuvers, thereby demonstrating fail-safe behavior. Additionally, some of these companies explicitly mention that, under specific conditions, they can continue to operate safely, albeit with more stringent constraints, which is characteristic of Fail Degraded behavior. This convergence of strategies highlights the importance of fault tolerance in ensuring the reliable operation of autonomous vehicles and underscores the industry's commitment to prioritizing safety in the development of autonomous technologies.

The list of analyzed companies has two notable absences: Tesla Autopilot and Baidu Apollo. To the best of the authors' knowledge, neither of these companies has publicly released a safety report detailing their approach to fault tolerance and safe operation.

VII. DISCUSSIONS

Despite increased efforts in recent years, the design and implementation of fault-tolerant architectures in connected and automated vehicles is still an open challenge. An analysis of

FIGURE 3. Scientific articles analyzed sorted by publication year

TABLE 4. Terms of the International Standards subject to be associated

SAE J3016	ISO 26262	ISO 21448	ISO/TR 4804
DDT Fallback	Emergency Operation	DDT Fallback	Minimal Risk Manoeuvre
Minimal risk condition	Safe State	Minimal risk condition	Minimal risk condition Safe state

the main aspects presented in this review is detailed in this section.

A. TEMPORAL EVOLUTION

After many years of research, CAVs have entered a large-scale testing phase, with companies such as Waymo [162], [173] or Zoox [174] deploying their vehicles in open traffic. Furthermore, traditional car manufacturers such as Mercedes-Benz [165], [175] and BMW [167] have received the approval to sell vehicles with Level 3 capabilities. Nevertheless, the technical development of CAVs is not yet completed, and the robustness and tolerance to failures remain open challenges [176]. Fig. 3 shows the scientific articles analyzed in this review sorted by publication year, which reflects the rising interest in research on this topic over the past two decades, which coincides with the commencement of large-scale testing. 2021 is considered an outlier due to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, and 2025 was halfway through when the article search ended.

B. TAXONOMY

A clear and complete taxonomy is essential for any research topic in order to accelerate and disseminate results. As noted by Stolte *et al.* [8], there are still different interpretations of terms in the literature. However, not only do scientific papers differ, but also, international standards use different terms to describe equivalent concepts. The terms subjected to be associated are gathered in Tab. 4

TABLE 5. Year of last publication and number of citations of the international standards

Standard	Year	Citations
SAE J3016	2021	19500
ISO 26262	2018	18300
ISO 21448	2022	2920
ISO/TR 4804	2020	218

ISO 26262 is an International Standard with a broader scope than automated vehicles. Hence, the definitions are not as specific to CAVs as the other International Standards. ISO/TR 4804 explicitly removes the term *DDT Fallback*, originally defined in SAE J3016, and replaces it with *Minimal Risk Manoeuvre*. However, the last updates of SAE J3016 and ISO 21448 maintain the term *DDT Fallback*. Furthermore, ISO 21448 explicitly defines *Minimal risk condition* as the analog of *Safe State* defined in ISO 26262. Nevertheless, ISO/TR 4804 includes both terms with limited differences between them. Tab. 5 collects the publication year of the last update of each international standard and the citation count, measured by the number of results of Google Scholar.

Although the differences are limited, unlike the differences in terminology in the literature, future updates should converge on a common taxonomy to help researchers and industry follow a common nomenclature. Preferably, they should converge on the taxonomy defined in SAE J3016 and ISO 21448, the most widely used international standards specific to automated driving.

C. TRENDS

After carrying out the analysis of the fault-related terminology in Section III, the degradation and operational strategies in Section IV, and the fallback strategies in Section V, some trends are identified.

Table 1 reflects different tendencies regarding the categorization of terminology as Fail-Operational, Fail-Degraded, Fail-Safe, or Unclassified. The majority of articles categorized in Fail-Operational and Fail-Degraded terms belong to localization, which is later reflected in the prevalence of these works in Tab. 2. By contrast, the articles classified in Fail-Safe terms are more evenly distributed. Furthermore, the articles belonging to the Communication and Driver-Vehicle Interaction terms are mainly categorized as Unclassified, which justifies their absence in Tab. 2 and Tab. 3. However, the reasons behind their absence are different. The articles classified in the Driver-Vehicle Interaction terms rely mainly on the driver to respond to the adverse situation, and so do not fall within the fault tolerance taxonomy described in ISO/TR 4804. Conversely, the Communication group collects causes that are not addressed from a fault tolerance perspective, creating a large research opportunity.

The two more populated strategies are the *localization sources fusion*, to overcome localization degradation and failures, and the *backup trajectory provision*, to handle various failures and functional insufficiencies. The fusion of the localization sources allows compensation for a single failure and continues the operation. However, this approach requires additional sensors and computational resources that increase the cost of the vehicle. The backup trajectory provision is widely employed as a Fail-Safe mechanism and, thus, is part of the fallback strategy, which is critical to ensure safety. However, very few papers in the Decision group propose methods for the continuation of operation even in a degraded mode. This could be a limiting factor for the mass deployment of automated vehicles and an area that needs further research.

The analysis of the main contributions of degradation and operational strategies in Section IV and fallback strategies in Section V shows a clear demarcation with respect to the validation environment. While 68% of the works proposing a degradation or operational approach (Tab. 2) are validated on a real vehicle or using a dataset containing real vehicle data, the percentage decreases to 17% in the case of the works proposing fallback strategies (Tab. 3). There are several reasons for these percentages. Fallback strategies are more difficult to implement in a real experiment due to the inherent potentially dangerous situation that a faulty implementation can create, as well as due to the need for a more complex road scenario (i.e., many fallback approaches are based on roadside parking). Another potential reason that may justify the percentage difference is based on the prevalence of works in Tab. 2 classified as “Acquisition, Localization and Perception”. These groups can work with recorded data since their output does not directly affect the vehicle movements, and various public datasets are available.

Furthermore, the industry analysis of Section VI shows how the trend across the CAV industry towards prioritizing fault tolerance is clear. Major industry players are converging on strategies centered around system redundancy, health monitoring, and fail-safe behavior, with the ability to execute fallback maneuvers in case of failures. Besides, some companies are also exploring Fail-Degraded capabilities, allowing them to continue operating safely, albeit with more stringent constraints, in the event of specific failures.

The safety-critical relevance of the field leads to large and diverse research opportunities, as already outlined in the manuscript. Examples of potentially beneficial lines of research include localization systems that do not require additional sensors and computational resources, planning algorithms that are more resilient to uncertainties, or the exploitation of infrastructure and cooperation using communication capabilities to overcome failures.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This article has presented a review of DDT fallback and fault tolerance techniques to overcome system failures and

functional insufficiencies in the context of connected and automated vehicles. It has pursued a special emphasis on the taxonomy defined by international standards, the most widely used terminology in the literature, and the analysis of the most relevant contributions. These terms are separated into degradation and operational strategies that continue the operation after the occurrence of the failure or functional insufficiencies, and fallback strategies that safely end the operation of the CAV, minimizing the risks involved. The results show a growing interest in the topic and a progressive implementation of tests in real vehicles, which is likely to lead to the transfer of these approaches to commercial automated vehicles soon, as well as the limitations of current solutions. Notably, the industry perspective confirms the importance of fault tolerance in ensuring safe and reliable operation of autonomous vehicles. Furthermore, there are great research opportunities on the topic, and it remains an active research area.

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